

The PGI gene had three alleles: Pgi³⁵, Pgi¹⁰⁰, and Pgi¹⁰⁵ designated as 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The IDH gene had two alleles: Idh⁹³ and Idh¹⁰⁰, designated as 1 and 2. The MDH gene had two alleles: Mdh¹⁰⁰ and Mdh¹⁰⁹, designated as 2 and 3.

The allele frequencies and the heterozygosities of the two populations are in Table 2. Biotype 1 had a slightly higher mean heterozygosity (\bar{H}) (0.068) than biotype 3 (0.023), mainly because of a higher number of heterozygotes at locus PCI.

As far as those three loci are concerned, biotype 1 exhibits more genetic variation than biotype 3. A more conclusive statement regarding the extent of variation could be obtained by increasing the number of protein loci investigated. □

Effect of temperature on brown planthopper (BPH) feeding

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We studied the effect of temperature on BPH feeding. BPH were collected from the stubble in rice fields on 5 Oct, after the crop was harvested and when mean temperature fell below 16 to 13°C.

Two 4th-instar nymphs and 2 adult BPH were placed in a mylar film cage and allowed to feed on 15-d-old plants of susceptible Milyang 23 for 24 h at a constant temperature. Area (mm²) of the honeydew spots excreted by BPH on Toyo No. 2 filter paper dipped in a solution of bromocresol green (2 mg/ml ethanol) was measured.

BPH feeding significantly decreased at lower temperatures (see table). At 9°C there was no feeding activity at nymph or adult stages. □

Area of honeydew spots excreted by BPH at different temperatures, Suweon, Korea.

Temp (°C)	Area (mm ²) ^a in 24 h		
	Nymphs	Adults	Mean
26	30.1 a	22.9 a	26.5
20	7.8 b	19.5 a	13.7
16	3.2 bc	3.5 b	3.4
13	5.4 bc	4.4 b	4.9
9	0.0 c	0.0 b	0.0

^a Mean for 2 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Weed control in dry-seeded lowland rice With bentazon and bentazon combined with 2,4-D

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Dry-seeded lowland rainfed rice has good potential in northeastern India, but heavy weed infestation is a serious constraint. In 1983, we evaluated bentazon and bentazon + 2,4-D for weed control.

In northeastern India, the typical dry-seeded field weed flora is 68-75% sedges, 15-20% broadleaf weeds, and 5-10% grasses. Bentazon was applied by a knapsack sprayer at 1.5 and 2.0 kg/ha alone or in combination with the amine salt of 2,4-D at 1.0 kg/ha with 1,000 litres of water/ha as a directed spray 15 d after rice germination.

Bentazon alone and bentazon + 2,4-D did not have a phytotoxic effect on rice seedlings. Bentazon + 2,4-D significantly

reduced weed population and weed dry matter accumulation compared with bentazon alone and grain yield was similar to that with conventional hand weeding (see table). With unchecked weed competition, grain yield was reduced 33.3%. □

Effect of different bentazon concentrations and bentazon combined with 2,4-D on rice grain yield and weed mortality, Bhubaneswar, India.^a

Treatment	Weeds (no./m ²) at 25 DAS	Weed dry wt (g/m ²) at 90 DAS	Grain yield t/ha
Bentazon @ 1.5 kg/ha	101.2	87	3.3 c
Bentazon @ 2.0 kg/ha	79.6	69	3.6 b
Bentazon @ 1.5 kg/ha + 2,4-D @ 1.0 kg/ha	59.4	57	3.9 a
Bentazon @ 2.0 kg/ha + 2,4-D @ 1.0 kg/ha	47.8	53	4.0 a
Conventional hand weeding (25 and 45 DAS)	398.6	28	4.2 a
Unweeded control	415.2	210	2.8 d
CD at 5%	19.4	10.4	0.27

^a DAS = days after seeding.

Effect of rice crop residue management on weed growth in lowland rice

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At TNAU, Coimbatore, in 1981 summer and monsoon seasons, we found that incorporating rice crop residues reduced weed dry matter production (DMP). Treatments were in a randomized split-plot design with three replications.

In summer, treatments were control, no residue incorporated (S₀); 10 t rice